

Influence of jute fibre and cement on the mechanical properties of raw earth mortar

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Raw earth mortar
Cement stabilisation
Jute fibre reinforcement
Compressed earth blocks
Numerical modelling
Cohesive zone model

ABSTRACT

In recent years, there has been an increased focus on the research of earthen construction, driven by the rising demand for low-cost and sustainable building materials. Numerous studies have investigated the properties of compressed earth blocks (CEBs), however, very few have examined the properties of earth-based mortar. Mortar is an essential component and further investigation is required to enhance the mechanical performance of CEB structures. The study focuses on raw earth mortar (REM), which is a rudimentary mix of water with natural earth consisting of sand, silt and clay. Through experimental investigation, the fresh and hardened properties of three REM mixes were examined to determine the influence of cement stabilisation and jute fibre reinforcement. Shear triplet CEB assemblages were manufactured and tested to determine the initial shear strength of each mortar mix. The addition of 20 mm jute fibre at 0.25 % by weight increased the compressive and flexural strength of cement-stabilised raw earth mortar by 12 % and 20 % respectively. The addition of jute fibre also enhanced the initial shear strength, angle of internal friction and coefficient of friction during shear triplet testing. Finite element analysis (FEA) was undertaken to model the failure mechanism of the CEB assemblages, employing the use of cohesive zone modelling. The results of the FEA provided a satisfactory correspondence to the behaviour observed during experimental analysis and were within ± 5.0 % of the expected values. The outcome of this investigation demonstrates the potential of REM and contributes to the development of low-cost and sustainable earth construction.

1. Introduction

In recent years, there has been an increased focus on the research and development of earthen construction, driven by the rising demand for low-cost and environmentally sustainable building materials [1]. Numerous experimental investigations have explored advances in compressed earth blocks (CEBs) [2–13], making it one of the most researched forms of earth construction. While significant attention has been given to the mechanical properties and durability characteristics of CEBs, there has been far less exploration into the materials commonly used to bond the blocks together, namely mortar. Mortar is a fundamental component in masonry construction. When wet, mortar acts as bedding material to accommodate any geometric irregularity within the individual masonry units and facilitates the stacking and assembly of walls and other structures. When hardened, mortar bonds the individual masonry units together and provides structural stability by transferring the compressive, tensile, and shear stresses between adjacent units.

Mortars are typically prepared by mixing a cementitious material, known as the binder, with inert fine aggregate and water. Before

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the 19th century, clay, gypsum, and lime were predominantly used as binders, with evidence of their application dating back to 6000 BCE [14,15]. In modern construction, Portland cement and lime are recognised as the most commonly used binders [14,16–18], although alternatives such as ground granulated blast furnace slag [19], fly ash [19], concrete waste powder [20] and pulverised calcined clay [21] have also been used. The inert fine aggregate is usually obtained from a natural source, such as river sand, or from manufactured or recycled aggregate of mineral origin. The proportions of a mortar mix will depend on the type of binder and fine aggregate used as well as the intended application and desired performance characteristics. In the present-day construction industry, the ratio of sand to cement typically ranges from 1:8 for low-strength mixes (≈ 2 MPa compressive strength), to 1:3 for high-strength mixes (≈ 12 MPa compressive strength) [22].

1.1. Earth based mortar

In contrast with modern-day sand-cement-based mortar, earth-based mortar incorporates earth as a partial or full replacement of the inert fine aggregate and/or binder. Earth-based mortars are typically used in conjunction with earth construction due to their structural compatibility, thermal performance, breathability, sustainability and aesthetic appeal [16,23]. There are several variations of earth-based mortar, as summarised in Table 1. This paper will distinguish between two main types of earth-based mortar, including mortar with earth (ME) and raw earth mortar (REM). The terms "earth" and "soil" are used interchangeably to describe the natural combination of sand, silt and clay that is found in the outer layer of the Earth's crust.

Mortar with earth, also known as cement-soil mortar [24], utilises a small portion of natural earth as a partial replacement of the inert fine aggregate. The composition of ME is commonly reported as a ratio of cement-soil-sand, with typical proportions ranging from 1-1-8 to 1-3-5 [24,25]. Within existing literature, the distinction between sand and soil is ambiguous, as soil will likely contain a portion of sand. Nevertheless, the clay content of the soil is often reported as the main variable. The clay content of the cement-soil mortar mix is varied either by diluting it with river sand or by removing certain sand fractions from the natural soil [24].

In contrast, REM is a rudimentary mix of water with natural earth consisting of sand, silt and clay. Unlike ME, REM uses earth in its natural "raw" form and is not blended or mixed with other inert fine aggregates. Within REM, the clay fraction acts as the binder and holds the inert particles of sand and silt together through electrostatic forces, cementation, capillarity, electromagnetic forces and friction [26,27]. REM is also known as mud mortar [24,28] and is recognised to be one of the oldest forms of mortar [15].

Compared to other earth-based building materials, there have been relatively few experimental investigations into REMs. However, there are some notable investigations documented in existing literature, as summarised in Table 1.

Within existing research into REM, there is conflicting information regarding the use of cementitious binders, such as Portland cement or hydrated lime. Some studies [42,43] discourage the use of cementitious binders due to the differences in relative stiffness and thermal expansion coefficients, which leads to cracking and separation between the REM and the block or wall to which it is bound. However, it is often noted in existing literature that the use of cementitious binders is a common practice in earth-based mortars [16]. Some studies tolerate or even recommend the use of cementitious binders [16,44], and others have shown that cementitious binders within earth-based mortar provide favourable mechanical properties when compared to sand-cement or sand-lime-based mortars [25].

Generally, REM has a low environmental impact due to the availability and accessibility of earth, which is an abundant natural resource that can be locally sourced [45]. The production of REM requires minimal processing which can be achieved using simple methods that are free from energy-demanding industrial equipment. The use of cementitious binders within REM will have an adverse environmental impact, due to the energy-intensive methods associated with their production [46]. Consequently, research is required to find alternative ways to improve the mechanical properties of REM and reduce the carbon intensity [47] of cement stabilisation. The use of natural fibre reinforcement is a potential solution to address this challenge.

Fibre reinforcement has been used to improve the mechanical properties of earth-based mortar, with existing studies into the influence of natural fibres such as pig hair [48], cow hair [49], bamboo [34], hemp fibre [16], and straw [49]. The addition of fibre reinforcement has been shown to increase compressive and flexural strength and decrease volumetric shrinkage and the presence of cracking caused by shrinkage [16,49]. The addition of natural fibre reinforcement is also known to decrease the life cycle greenhouse gas emissions of mortar [34]. An investigation by Pederngana et al. [49] assessed the compressive strength and flexural strength of 30 earth mortars for plasters and renders, with different quantities and different types of sand and fibre. It was found that thin and flexible

Table 1
Variations of Earth-based Mortar and the Nomenclature Adopted in this Study.

Nomenclature		Dry Constituents				References
Definition	Acronym	Sand	Earth	Binder ^a	Fibre ^b	
Modern Building Mortar	–	✓		✓		[17,18,29–31]
Mortar with Earth	ME	✓	✓	✓		[23,25,29,32–35]
Raw Earth Mortar	REM		✓			[28,36–40]
Stabilised Raw Earth Mortar	SREM		✓	✓		[35,36,41]
Fibre Reinforced Stabilised Raw Earth Mortar	FRSREM		✓	✓	✓	–

^a Cementitious binder typically consists of Portland Cement and/or Hydrated Lime.

^b Fibre reinforcement typically consists of polymer or natural fibres.

fibres with high tensile strength improved the mechanical properties of earth-based mortar, while thick brittle fibres had the opposite effect. Furthermore, it was found that the incorporation of fibre at $<0.5\%$ by weight increased the tensile strength of the mortar, while quantities above 0.5% demonstrated a gradual decrease in tensile strength with increasing proportions [50]. Jute was selected as the natural fibre reinforcement for this research. It is one of the most versatile, cost-effective and widely available fibres [51,52]. Despite its high tensile strength and low density [53–56], jute remains under-utilised in existing research.

Although there are some existing studies into REM, these studies are scarce. Because of this, it is important to advance our understanding of the mechanical properties of earth-based mortar and the influence of cementitious binder and natural fibre reinforcement.

1.2. Existing test methods

While there are no British Standards (BS) or European Standards (EN) related to the manufacture or testing of earth-based mortars, there is some technical guidance originating from Africa [57,58], New Zealand [59,60], and Germany [61]. The German Institute for Standardisation (Deutsches Institut für Normung) DIN 18946:2018 [61] is commonly referenced in existing literature and outlines the manufacture and testing requirements of earth mortars. When used for load-bearing applications, DIN 18946:2018 [61] requires earth-based mortars to have a minimum compressive strength of 2.00 MPa and a minimum initial shear strength of 0.04 MPa. DIN 18946:2018 [61] allows the use of organic additives such as plant parts and fibres, animal hair and shredded chemically untreated wood, but does not cover cement or lime-stabilised earth mortar. As a result, the performance criteria of fibre reinforcement in combination with cement stabilised earth mortar is unknown.

Within existing experimental investigations, the compressive and flexural strength of earth-based mortar is commonly determined through the testing of mortar prisms, cubes or cylinders [16,23,49]. However, evaluating the discrete characteristics of the masonry unit and the mortar separately is not enough to understand the strength or behaviour of the masonry when acting as a system [25].

The initial shear strength (identified by f_{vo}) is an important engineering parameter which is utilised in the assessment and verification of masonry subjected to shear loading and in-plane lateral forces [30,62]. Moreover, this parameter finds application in seismic design and Finite Element Analysis (FEA) of masonry structures [63]. The initial shear strength is a measure of the in-plane shear strength of the bond interface and mortar joint and is commonly determined through shear triplet testing outlined in BS EN 1052–3:2002 [17,38,64,65].

The most common test procedure utilises a 3-block test configuration as per the requirements of BS EN 1052–3:2002 [64]. However, a previous study [30] conducted a series of experimental tests and numerical simulations on earth block masonry to investigate the difference between 3-block, 4-block and 6-block shear triplet test configuration, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The analysis revealed that the shear strength of the 4-block and 6-block configurations was greater than the shear strength of the 3-block configuration due to the incorporation of the horizontal mortar joints. Although a difference in shear strength was identified, it remains unclear which test configuration provides the most accurate and reliable measure of initial shear strength. It is for this reason that the standard procedure defined in BS EN 1052–3:2002 [64], which utilises a 3-block configuration, is usually adopted.

Very few studies have investigated the initial shear strength of REM, as summarised in Table 2. The existing studies show a significant variation in the results of initial shear strength, ranging from 0.018 to 0.16 MPa. The initial shear strength is influenced by several factors, including the mortar composition, the surface characteristics of the masonry unit and the moisture content of the masonry unit at the time of construction [25,38,66]. The method of manufacturing the shear triplet samples and the process of pre-wetting the surfaces of the block before the application of mortar is also known to have a significant influence on the initial shear strength achieved [38,39]. In one study [39], samples subjected to pre-wetting achieved an initial shear strength 3.5 times greater than

Fig. 1. Type of Shear Triplet Testing: 3-Block (A), 4-Block (B), and 6-Block (C). Arrows Indicate the Direction of Loading, i. Force to Induce Shear Stress, ii. Precompression Load, iii. Supports.

Table 2
Initial shear strength of raw earth mortar and compressed earth blocks.

Description of Block	Surface Treatment	Type of Mortar	Compressive Strength of Mortar (MPa)	Initial Shear Strength (MPa)	Angle of Internal Friction (°)	Ref
Natural Earth	–	REM	2.93	0.10	50	[38]
Natural Earth	Wetted	REM	2.93	0.16	37	
Natural Earth	–	REM	–	0.014	–	[39]
Natural Earth	Wetted	REM	–	0.049	–	
Natural Earth	Wetted	REM	3.32	0.018	49	[40]
Lime Stabilised Earth	–	SREM	1.19	0.048	N/A	[41]
Lime Stabilised Earth	–	SREM	1.19	0.057	N/A	

samples without pre-wetting. This highlights the importance of pre-wetting to ensure a sufficient bond between the mortar and the block.

1.3. Numerical modelling of masonry with earth mortar

While experimental analysis is necessary to determine the fundamental material properties of masonry, the use of finite element analysis (FEA) has made it possible to simulate the behaviour and evaluate the performance of masonry assemblages and large masonry structures. The main advantage of FEA is its versatility and capability to model different configurations, loading conditions, and material properties, whilst avoiding the time and cost associated with large-scale experimental analysis. FEA has proven successful in modelling conventional masonry structures [67], individual CEBs of alternative geometries [5], interlocking CEBs stacked on top of one another [68] and earthen structures subjected to seismic loading [69]. Despite the known benefits of FEA, its application in modelling CEBs and earth-based mortar has been extremely limited.

In the past, few attempts have been made at modelling earth block masonry assemblages. A previous study [40] investigated macro and micro-modelling methods to simulate the behaviour of masonry wallettes. Macro-modelling was undertaken by considering the wallette as an equivalent homogeneous material, based on Rankine/Von Mises plasticity, constant shear retention law, brittle tensile behaviour, and compressive behaviour observed during experimental analysis. The macro-modelling method was reported to obtain satisfactory resemblance to experimental data, but it did not consider interface failure mechanisms and failed to reproduce accurate cracking patterns. In contrast, micro-modelling was undertaken by considering the individual masonry blocks bonded by potential fracture/slip lines at the joint interfaces. This method was found to produce satisfactory results and successfully simulated the crack and fracture patterns observed during experimental analysis. Consequently, the micro-modelling approach was considered to be a viable tool for predicting the collapse mechanism of earth-based masonry structures.

Due to the lack of studies that have used FEA to model the interface between CEBs and earth-based mortar, there is significant potential for alternative and improved modelling techniques to be explored. The use of a cohesive zone model (CZM) appears to be a possible alternative. A CZM is a fracture model that enables fracture or delamination along an interface, whereby fracture formation is considered a gradual phenomenon and the separation of the crack surfaces takes place across a cohesive zone [70]. The use of CZM to define the interface between mortar and masonry has proven successful in simulating conventional masonry structures [67], but its application to CEBs and earth-based mortar is novel.

1.4. Knowledge gap

Existing research into the mechanical properties of REM and how it performs when subjected to shear loading is very limited. While some studies have examined the compressive strength and other basic characteristics of REM, there is a distinct lack of comprehensive research exploring its behaviour under shear forces. Understanding the shear performance of REM is crucial for evaluating its suitability for various construction applications and optimising its structural design. Closing this research gap is essential for advancing our knowledge of REM and promoting its effective utilisation in sustainable building practices. Furthermore, there are no existing studies on the influence of natural fibre reinforcement on the mechanical properties of REM. Therefore, the investigation into fibre reinforced cement stabilised raw earth mortar (FRSREM) and the shear behaviour of CEB assemblages holds unique significance within the existing literature.

Within this paper, the properties and performance of three different REMs are established and compared through experimental investigation. The results of the experimental investigation are applied to develop advanced FEA simulations that utilise innovative CZM techniques to simulate the mortar-block interface. The holistic objective of this research is to expand existing knowledge and identify potential improvements in REMs to further develop low-cost and environmentally friendly construction and building materials around the world. This research aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UNSDGs) [71] and can contribute to the creation of more sustainable cities and communities (UNSDG 11). The research specifically supports target 11.1 [72], which aims to upgrade slums and ensure that everyone has access to adequate, safe, and affordable housing and basic services by 2030.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Material preparation and classification

2.1.1. Properties of soil

A BS 8601:2013 [73] compliant subsoil, obtained from Hampshire (South of England, UK) was used to manufacture the CEBs and the earth mortars. BS 8601:2013 subsoil is a sandy loam which can be described as per BS 5930:2015 [74] as an orange-brown clayey SAND. BS 8601:2013 subsoil was selected due to its high sand content and relatively high clay content, making it suitable for the manufacture of CEBs and mortars. Although the sand content exceeded the recommended limit for compressed earth mix designs [75], the relatively high clay content provided sufficient adhesion during the manufacture of test samples. The BS 8601:2013 subsoil was prepared by passing through a 2.00 mm sieve to remove any gravel (>2.0 mm) and was dried to eliminate any natural moisture content.

The properties of the BS 8601:2013 subsoil were measured as per BS 1377-2:2022 [76], including the optimum moisture content (OMC), maximum dry density (MDD), liquid limit (LL), plastic limit (PL) and particle size distribution (PSD). The PSD (sieve analysis) was undertaken as per BS 1377-2:2022, Part 10 [76], and further analysis of the clay and silt content was performed using a Mastersizer 3000 laser diffraction particle size analyser [77]. The results are presented in Table 3.

2.1.2. Properties of jute fibre

Jute was used as the natural fibre reinforcement within the FRSREM. Jute was chosen as boasts high tensile strength (typically ranging from 215 to 800 MPa), low density (730–1500 kg/m³) [53–56] and is known to be one of the most affordable and accessible natural fibres [51,52]. Jute was acquired in the form of jute yarn, also known as twine, which is comprised of numerous interwoven bast fibre bundles. A single source of jute yarn was used in this investigation to reduce the natural variation of the fibre properties. The mechanical properties of the jute yarn were established during a previous experimental investigation conducted by the authors [4], as summarised in Table 4. The jute fibre was cut into lengths of 20 mm ± 2 mm and incorporated in the FRSREM at a quantity of 0.25 % by weight. The fibre length and fibre quantity were selected based on recommendations outlined in existing research [78–81].

2.1.3. Mortar mix design

Three different mortar mixes were studied, including REM, SREM and FRSREM, as presented in Table 5. Tarmac blue circle general purpose cement (BS EN 197-1:2011 CEM II 32.5R) [82] was used as the cementitious binder in SREM and FRSREM, and was incorporated at a quantity of 1:4 by volume. The amount of cement was selected based on typical quantities used in existing literature [16,23,25,29]. The quantity of each material was measured by mass, as this could be easily and accurately measured by the use of weighing scales. To determine the quantities by mass, the bulk density of the BS8601:2013 subsoil and cement was measured by filling and weighing a container of known volume. The BS8601:2013 subsoil and cement were found to have a mean bulk density of 910 kg/m³ and 1088 kg/m³, respectively. With this information, the material quantities were converted from percentage volume to percentage mass, as presented in Table 5.

The water content of the mortar was determined through qualitative assessment. Trial batches were produced with different water contents and the behaviour and characteristics of the wet mortar were visually assessed based on consistency, adhesion and workability. Once the optimum mix was discovered, the samples were dried, revealing that 30 % water content was required to achieve optimum workability. Following this discovery, 30 % water content was added to each of the mortar mixes, presented in Table 5.

The moisture content required to achieve the optimum workability of the mortar was found to be significantly higher than the OMC of the soil at MDD, obtained from the Proctor test. This is due to the additional moisture content required to achieve sufficient workability. The amount of water required to achieve optimum workability of the mortar was found to be approximately 10 % less than the LL of the soil.

Table 3
Properties of BS 8601:2013 subsoil.

Property	BS 8601 Subsoil
Proctor Test	
Optimum Moisture Content (%)	17.5
Maximum Dry Density (kg/m ³)	1680
Atterberg Limits	
Liquid Limit, LL (%)	33.7
Plastic Limit, PL (%)	25.9
Plasticity Index, PI (%)	7.8
Soil Classification	
Unified Soil Classification System	ML
Particle Size Distribution	
Gravel (>2.0 mm) (%)	0.0
Sand (2.0–0.063 mm) (%)	68.0
Silt (0.063–0.002 mm) (%)	15.0
Clay (<0.002 mm) (%)	17.0

Table 4
Properties of jute yarn [4].

Property:	Value:
Number of Bast Fibre Bundles Per Yarn	119
Density (kg/m ³)	1122
Cross-Sectional Area (mm ²)	0.2
Tensile Strength (N/mm ²)	248
Natural Moisture Content Under Ambient Conditions (20 °C, 58 % Relative Humidity)	13
Time to Reach Fibre Saturation (Minutes)	50
Moisture Absorption at Saturation (%)	205
Cross-Sectional Swelling at Saturation (%)	19

Table 5
Quantity of dry constituents.

Description	Mix Reference	Mass (%)		
		BS 8601 Subsoil	Cement	Jute Fibre
Raw Earth Mortar	REM	100.00	-	-
Stabilised Earth Mortar	SREM	77.00	23.00	-
Fibre Reinforced Cement Stabilised Raw Earth Mortar	FRSREM	76.75	23.00	0.25

2.2. Manufacture of test samples

A series of mortar prisms, CEBs and shear triplet samples were manufactured and tested as part of this investigation, as presented in Table 6.

2.2.1. Manufacture of CEBs

The CEBs contained an earth mixture comprising of BS 8601:2013 subsoil and water (17.5 % by weight). The water content was based on the OMC of the soil at MDD, obtained using the method defined in BS 1377-2:2022, Part 11.3 [76]. The quantities of

Table 6
Test Specimens (Dimensions in mm).

Sample	Geometry	Experimental Methods	
		Type of Test	Number of Specimens Per Test, Per Mix Design
Mortar Half Prisms		Compression Test	6
Mortar Prisms		Flexural Test	3
Compressed Earth Blocks		Compression Test	5
		Flexural Test	5
Shear Triplets		Shear Triplet Test	3

BS8601:2013 subsoil and water were carefully measured and then mixed for 5 min at 50 revolutions per minute using a standard duty forced action pan mixer [83]. The CEBs were manufactured in batches of 5 to prevent the earth mixture from drying out.

CEBs measuring 150 mm (L) x 75 mm (W) x 50 mm (H) were manufactured using the University of Portsmouth half-scale block mould, shown in Fig. 2, following the detailed methodology previously developed by the authors at the University of Portsmouth [3]. A force-controlled method of compaction was utilised, also known as constant peak stress-variable stroke compaction. The samples were manufactured using a Zwick/Roell Z250 universal testing machine [84] with a consistent target pressure of 1.25 MPa [25].

Once manufactured, the samples were dried at 30 °C in a Genlab MINO/100 oven [85] and reweighed following the procedure detailed in BS 1377-2:2022 [76]. Once a consistent weight was observed ± 0.01 g, the samples were considered to have reached hygrothermal equilibrium. To evaluate the amount of shrinkage throughout the drying process, the samples were weighed and measured before testing.

2.2.2. Manufacture of mortar prisms

To produce the mortar, the BS 8601:2013 subsoil was passed through a 2.00 mm sieve to remove any large particles. The dry constituents for each mix were then weighed out, as per the proportions detailed in Table 5. The dry constituents were then combined with 30 % water content, and mechanically mixed for 5 min using a table-top planetary mixer [86]. Each mix was prepared consecutively to prevent the mortar from drying out.

Once the mortar had been mixed, the consistency of fresh mortar was tested and recorded using a flow table, as per BS EN 1015-3:1999 [87]. The mortar prisms were then manufactured as per BS EN 1015-11:2019 [88], and left to dry/cure for 28 days before testing. To evaluate the amount of shrinkage, the samples were weighed and measured after 28 days, prior to destructive testing.

2.2.3. Manufacture of shear triplet samples

The shear triplet test samples were assembled as per the requirements outlined in BS EN 1052-3:2002 [64]. The size of the blocks deviated from the requirements of the aforementioned standard, however the aspect ratio of the blocks remained within specification. An existing investigation [30] found that the size of blocks used in a 3-block shear triplet test had little influence on the distribution of shear stress in the mortar joint.

Before applying the mortar, the surface of each block was prepared by spraying 10 ml of water evenly across the surface to aid adhesion. The water was allowed to soak into the block for 60 s before the mortar was applied. The process of pre-wetting is recommended [38,39] to ensure a suitable bond between the mortar and the block. Moisture movement from the fresh mortar bed joint into the pores of the block is essential for developing the mechanical interlock [25].

The shear triplet samples were assembled using a 10 mm (± 1.00 mm) layer of mortar. The specimens were checked for linear alignment and level using a set-square and a spirit level. Once assembled, a 50 N weight was applied to each shear triplet specimen, providing a uniform stress of approximately 4.4×10^{-3} MPa, in accordance with the requirements of BS EN 1052-3:2002 [64]. The shear triplet samples were left undisturbed and allowed to dry/cure for 28 days before testing.

2.3. Destructive testing

Test standards produced by British Standards (BS), Eurocodes (EN) and the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) were adopted where appropriate. This approach has been taken by numerous existing studies into CEBs and earth-based mortars [5,11,13,89-91]. All tests were performed using a Zwick/Roell Z250 [84] universal testing machine.

2.3.1. Testing of CEBs

The compression tests of the CEBs were conducted in accordance with BS EN 772-1:2011 [92], using a load rate of 0.05 MPa/s. The

Fig. 2. – Photographs of the university of portsmouth half-scale block mould during compression (A) and post manufacture (B).

Zwick/Roell Z250 measured and recorded the force and deformation throughout the test, which was then used to calculate stress and strain. The load at which the block failed was recorded and maximum compressive stress was calculated as per BS EN 772-1:2011, part 9 [92].

The flexural (three-point bending) tests of the CEBs were conducted in accordance with BS EN 12390-5:2019 [93], using a load rate of 62.5 N/s. The Zwick/Roell Z250 measured and recorded the force and deformation throughout the test, which was then used to calculate stress and strain. The load at which the block failed was recorded and flexural strength was calculated as per BS EN 12390-5:2019, formula A.2. Once the flexural strength was determined, it was possible to estimate the uniaxial tensile stress from existing empirical relationships observed within low-strength concrete [94].

2.3.2. Testing of hardened mortar

Mortar prisms were used to determine the flexural strength, as per BS EN 1015-11:2019, Part 8 [88]. Due to the anticipated strength of the mortar, a load rate of 10 N/s was selected and applied. The Zwick/Roell Z250 measured and recorded the force and deformation throughout the test, which was then used to calculate stress and strain. The flexural strength was determined as per the equation outlined in BS EN 1015-11:2019, part 8.3 [88].

Following flexural testing, the mortar prisms were separated into two halves and tested in compression, as per BS EN 1015-11:2019, part 9 [88]. A load rate of 50 N/s was applied until failure, as per Annex B of BS EN 1015-11:2019 [88]. The Zwick/Roell Z250 measured and recorded the force and deformation throughout the test, which was then used to calculate stress and strain. The load at which the half-prism failed was recorded and maximum compressive stress was calculated.

2.3.3. Determination of initial shear strength

The determination of initial shear strength was performed as per Section 8.2.1 of BS EN 1052-3:2002 [64] (Procedure A). A Zwick/Roell Z250 [84] was used to apply the load parallel to the mortar joints, which induces shear stress within the sample, as shown in Fig. 3. The load was increased at a rate of 1125 N/min, which is equivalent to 0.1 MPa/min shear stress across the shear plane.

A load perpendicular to the mortar joints, also known as the precompression force (F_{pi}), was applied and measured using a CBES-20,000 kg compression load cell [95] with a Vishay P3 strain indicator and recorder [96]. Procedure A of BS EN 1052-3:2002 [64] was followed, whereby the precompression force was applied at 1125 N (0.10 MPa), 3375 N (0.30 MPa), and 5625 N (0.50 MPa). 10 mm steel plates and 8 mm softboard were used to distribute the precompression force evenly across the sample.

The maximum load parallel to the mortar joints ($F_{i,max}$) was recorded and used to determine the shear strength (f_{voi}) of each specimen, as per BS EN 1052-3:2002, part 9 [64]. The results were evaluated by plotting shear strength (f_{voi}) against the pre-compressive stress (f_{pi}).

2.4. Non-destructive testing

A Tescan MIRA3 field emission gun [97] and a Zeiss EVO MA10 [98] were used to perform scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to investigate the properties of the mortar on a micro level. The purpose of the SEM was to visually examine the mortar bond interface zone, evaluate the influence of jute fibre reinforcement, and capture high-magnification photos of the surface porosity of the mortar mixes.

To view the mortar bond interface zone, samples were cast in resin, cut and polished to provide a clear sectional view of the bond. A Quorum Q150R S [99] was used to prepare the samples with a gold and palladium sputter coating at a ratio of 80:20. The coating was applied to prevent charging of the specimen and to increase the signal-to-noise ratio. The SEM was performed using a backscatter detector and an acceleration voltage of 20 kV. Due to the size and porosity of the samples, a variable pressure aperture was adopted instead of the high vacuum setting.

Fig. 3. Photograph of shear triplet test before testing (A) and after testing (B).

2.5. Numerical modelling

An FEA software, ANSYS Workbench 2024R1 [100], was used to model the failure mechanism of the shear triplet test and provide a comparison with the results obtained from the experimental analysis. The static structural analysis system within ANSYS Workbench 2024R1 was used to establish the engineering data, geometry, model, setup, solution and results. The methodology outlined in this study expands upon existing FEA modelling undertaken by the authors [5].

Where possible, the properties of each material were obtained from the experimental analysis, as summarised in Table 7. Values such as Poisson's ratio and the shear transfer coefficients were obtained from existing literature [40,68,101–103]. The flexural strength of the blocks and mortars was determined experimentally from which the tensile strength was estimated based on known empirical relationships observed within low-strength concrete [94].

To define the multilinear material behaviour, the average compressive stress/strain relationship of each material was determined from the experimental results, as per the example illustrated in Fig. 4. This data was tabulated and input using the engineering data interface within the static structural analysis system.

The three-dimensional configuration of the shear triplet assembly was created using ANSYS SpaceClaim 3D [104] and was modelled to replicate the size and geometry of the specimens tested in the experimental analysis. The boundary conditions were also established to simulate the conditions experienced during testing. The bottom platen of the test machine was modelled to provide a fixed support within the simulation, while the top platen was free to move in the direction of the applied load. The load was applied at the same rate utilised in the experimental analysis, as detailed in section 2.3. A frictional contact was used to model the interface between the platens and the test specimen.

A CZM was used to model the mortar-block interface. This approach has proven successful in simulating conventional masonry structures [67], but its application to earth-based masonry is novel. The CZM utilised separation-distance based debonding and considered a mixed debonding interface mode. The maximum equivalent tangential contact stress was taken as the initial shear strength obtained from the experimental analysis. Furthermore, the contact gap and tangential slip at completion of debonding were taken from the force–deformation data obtained from testing. The maximum normal contact stress was estimated based on empirical relationships between mortar compressive strength and tensile bond strength [33,105]. The results from the shear triplet testing at 0.10 MPa, 0.30 MPa and 0.50 MPa precompression were used to calibrate and validate the CSM. The parameters of the CZM are summarised in Table 8.

SOLID186 elements were utilised as their application has proven successful in modelling masonry construction and individual masonry units within the existing literature [102,106,107]. SOLID186 is a 20-node solid element that exhibits quadratic displacement behaviour and has three degrees of freedom at each node; translations in the nodal x, y, and z directions. It was utilised in conjunction with CONTA174 and TARGE170 elements to model the surface interactions. The mesh size and step control were determined following an iterative and thorough sequence of sensitivity analysis. A mesh size of 10.0 mm × 10.0 mm was utilised throughout the modelling to ensure acceptable accuracy.

Following the successful development of the CZM model, the results obtained from experimental analysis were used to simulate the behaviour of a 1240 mm (H) × 1240 mm (W) × 150 mm (T) masonry assemblage subjected to a diagonal shear test, as per ASTM E519-E519M:2022 [108]. The masonry assemblage contained CEBs with individual dimensions 300 mm (L) × 150 mm (W) × 100 mm (H) and was modelled with a 14 mm thick mortar joint. The wall assemblages were modelled without edge loading, as per the standard procedure outlined in ASTM E519-E519M:2022. The addition of edge loading (defined in Annex A1 of ASTM E519-E516M:2022) is known to significantly increase the results of shear stress, strain and modulus of rigidity [108]. The results of the wall simulation are

Table 7
Summary of data used in the FEA model.

Parameter	Mix Reference			
	CEB	REM	SREM	FRSREM
Dry Density (kg/m ³)	1516	1577	1571	1544
Poisson's ratio, ν	0.2 ^a	0.2 ^a	0.2 ^a	0.2 ^a
Ultimate Compressive Stress, f_c (MPa)	2.35	1.92	5.64	6.31
Compression Modulus, E_c (MPa)	106	125	575	625
Multilinear Stress-Strain Data (Compression):	–	–	–	–
Data Point 1 (Strain-Stress)	0.0000–0.00	0.0000–0.00	0.0000–0.00	0.0000–0.00
Data Point 2 (Strain-Stress)	0.0160–1.70	0.0120–1.50	0.0080–4.60	0.0084–5.25
Data Point 3 (Strain-Stress)	0.0200–1.99	0.0157–1.79	0.0100–5.28	0.0110–6.00
Data Point 4 (Strain-Stress)	0.0280–2.35	0.0193–1.92	0.0125–5.64	0.0141–6.31
Data Point 5 (Strain-Stress)	0.0350–2.08	0.0300–1.48	0.0300–2.55	0.0300–5.34
Ultimate Flexural Stress, f_f (MPa)	0.58	0.50	1.20	1.44
Ultimate Tensile Stress, f_t (MPa)	0.26 ^a	0.21 ^a	0.62 ^a	0.69 ^a
Shear transfer coefficients for an open crack, β_o	0.1 ^a	0.1 ^a	0.1 ^a	0.1 ^a
Shear transfer coefficients for a closed crack, β_c	0.1 ^a	0.1 ^a	0.1 ^a	0.1 ^a
Initial Shear Strength, f_{vo} (MPa)	–	0.198	0.262	0.280
Angle of Internal Friction, α (Degrees)	–	6.59	8.91	11.62
Coefficient of Friction, μ	–	0.116	0.157	0.206

^a Values derived from existing literature [40,68,101–103].

Fig. 4. Stress-Strain Curve Obtained from Testing (A), Simplified Stress-Strain Curve used in FEA (B). Example Dataset from Compression Testing of Mortar Half Prisms (REM).

Table 8
Summary of data used in the CZM.

Parameter	Mix Reference		
	REM	SREM	FRSREM
Mode	Mixed	Mixed	Mixed
Tangential Slip Under Normal Compression	Yes	Yes	Yes
Maximum Normal Contact Stress (MPa)	0.112	0.155	0.165
Contact Gap at the Completion of Debonding (mm)	0.28	0.31	0.38
Maximum Equivalent Tangential Contact Stress (MPa)	0.198	0.262	0.280
Tangential Slip at the completion of debonding (mm)	1.65	1.85	2.25
Artificial Damping Coefficient (s)	1 ^a	1 ^a	1 ^a
Power Law Exponential for Mixed-Mode Debonding	4 ^a	4 ^a	4 ^a

^a Determined through sensitivity analysis.

expressed in terms of shear stress (S_s), shear strain (γ) and modulus of rigidity (G), as calculated following part 7 of ASTM E519-E519M:2022 [108].

Due to the numerical size limitations associated with the academic license of ANSYS Workbench 2024R1 [100], the minimum mesh size of the wall model was limited to 25 mm with an adaptive resolution of 1. Sensitivity analysis was performed to assess the influence of mesh size ranging from 25 mm to 100 mm, and it was found that a mesh size of 50 mm (29,875 nodes) was sufficient to achieve satisfactory results.

2.6. Statistical test

Minitab 17.3.1 [109] was used to perform statistical analysis (ANOVA with Tukey pairwise comparison) to assess the statistical significance of the variables. Statistically significant differences are indicated by different letters (A, B, C). Results that are in the same category, i.e. share the same letter, are not significantly different at p-value <0.05 (5%). The results of each test should be interpreted independently.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Properties of CEBs

During the manufacture of CEBs, a force-controlled compaction end-point was utilised, also known as constant peak stress-variable stroke compaction, with a target compaction pressure of 1.25 MPa. This method of manufacture ensures a consistent compaction pressure, however, due to the natural variation of PSD, initial arrangement of soil particles, mineral composition, and moisture content

of the soil, this method produces blocks with differing heights and densities. The mean dry density of the CEBs was found to be 1516.3 kg/m³ with a standard deviation (σ) of 9.9 kg/m³, which was less than the target dry density, indicating that a greater compaction pressure was required during manufacture.

The CEBs exhibited a mean compressive strength of 2.35 MPa ($\sigma = 0.39$ MPa) and a mean flexural strength of 0.58 MPa ($\sigma = 0.07$ MPa). Considering the known correlation between dry density and compressive strength [25,26], it is likely that the CEBs would have achieved a higher compressive strength had the target dry density been reached. However, as the CEBs remained constant throughout the study, this did not influence the experimental investigation into the raw earth mortars.

3.2. Properties of earth mortar

3.2.1. Mortar flow

Table 9 presents the percentage flow of the three mortar types. The results show that the addition of cement to the REM increased the mortar flow, while the addition of fibre reinforcement decreased the mortar flow. The presence of fibres within the mortar provides mechanical resistance to the movement of particles and reduces the overall workability of the mixture. Furthermore, due to the hydrophilic nature of jute [4], the fibre may absorb moisture from the mortar mix, reducing the overall free water content available to provide lubrication. The combination of mechanical resistance and water absorption contributes to the reduction in mortar flow.

3.2.2. Dry density

The dry density of the REM and SREM were very similar, although on average the SREM demonstrated a slight reduction in density, as shown in Table 9. This finding is consistent with existing literature [26], whereby the addition of cement to soil is known to reduce the dry density in soils which compact well. The incorporation of jute fibre within the FRSREM was found to lower the overall density of the mortar by approximately 2.0 %. This is due to the relatively low-density fibre (1122 kg/m³) occupying space within the sample that would have otherwise been occupied by the relatively high-density mortar (≈ 1574 kg/m³). Furthermore, the incorporation of fibre may introduce voids within the mortar which also contribute to the reduction in density.

3.2.3. Linear shrinkage

The REM specimens demonstrated the largest average linear shrinkage of 4.0 % (Table 9), which is the upper bound of allowable shrinkage, as defined by DIN 18946:2018 [61]. This level of shrinkage is due to the shrink-swell behaviour of the clay minerals present within the BS 8601 Subsoil. In contrast, the SREM specimens demonstrated an average linear shrinkage of 0.88 %, indicating that the addition of cement significantly reduced the amount of shrinkage of the BS 6801:2013 subsoil. This finding is consistent with Houben & Guillaud [26], who reported that cement stabilisation reduces the magnitude of drying shrinkage in soils. The incorporation of jute fibre within the FRSREM was shown to reduce the linear shrinkage further, to an average of 0.57 %. This addition of fibre to earth-based mortar has been reported to reduce the linear shrinkage in existing studies [49] and is caused by the interlocking influence of the fibres that hold the soil particles together, which resists deformation that occurs during the drying process. In comparison, modern-day sand-cement-based mortar typically exhibits between 0.03 and 0.11 % linear shrinkage after 28 days [25,110], which is

Table 9
Properties of Mortar (Mean Values where n = 5, \pm Standard Deviation).

Mix Reference:	Flow (%)		Dry Density (kg/m ³)	Shrinkage (%)
REM	51 \pm 4		1577 \pm 31	4.00 \pm 0.50
SREM	64 \pm 7		1571 \pm 28	0.88 \pm 0.18
FRSREM	45 \pm 6		1544 \pm 17	0.57 \pm 0.24

significantly less than the shrinkage observed in the REM, SREM and FRSREM specimens. This is due to the clay content within the REM, which is not found in modern-day sand-cement-based mortar [111].

3.2.4. Compressive strength

It can be seen from Fig. 5A that the REM specimens demonstrated the lowest average compressive strength of 1.92 MPa ($\sigma = 0.13$ MPa), while the SREM specimens achieved an average compressive strength of 5.64 MPa ($\sigma = 0.53$ MPa), representing an increase of approximately 194 %. This significant increase in compressive strength is due to the incorporation of cement which, when combined with water, initiates chemical reactions leading to the formation of hydration products. The hydration products, such as Calcium-Silicate-Hydrates (C-S-H) [112], bond the inert sand particles together, creating a solid interlocked material matrix. The addition of cement is widely recognised to enhance the mechanical properties of material mixtures [113–118], and these results demonstrate the effectiveness of increasing the bearing capacity of REM. In comparison, the FRSREM specimens achieved an average compressive strength of 6.33 MPa ($\sigma = 0.45$ MPa), representing an increase of 230 % and 12 % compared to the REM and SREM specimens, respectively. The compressive strength of the REM aligns with findings from previous studies [38–41], while the SREM and FRSREM demonstrate significantly higher values than those reported in the existing literature. Based on the results of the compressive strength testing, the REM can be classified as an M1 mortar, and the SREM and FRSREM can both be classified as M5 mortars, as per definitions outlined in BS EN 998-2:2016 [19] and DIN 18946:2018 [61].

During the compression tests, the REM and SREM behaved similarly to a conventional concrete test cube, with vertical tensile cracking followed by crushing and spalling. The incorporation of cement in the SREM and FRSREM samples resulted in a lower strain at peak stress, which is consistent with existing studies [119,120]. This is an important observation that indicates cement stabilised raw earth mortar may not be suitable for applications that demand flexible mortars that can accommodate large strain values. However, the fibre reinforcement within FRSREM prevented sudden and catastrophic failure of the test samples and demonstrated significant post-failure residual strength.

3.2.5. Flexural strength

The results of the three-point bending tests demonstrated a similar trend to the compression tests, as presented in Fig. 5B. The REM specimens demonstrated the lowest average flexural strength of 0.50 MPa ($\sigma = 0.03$ MPa), while SREM and FRSREM achieved 1.20 MPa ($\sigma = 0.08$ MPa) and 1.44 MPa ($\sigma = 0.11$ MPa) respectively. On average, the flexural strength was found to be between 21 and 26 % of the compressive strength, which is similar to the relationship observed in other brittle materials, such as concrete [121–123].

The increase in compressive and tensile strength of the FRSREM samples may be attributed to the fibre's ability to redistribute stress across the samples, preventing the propagation of cracks and inhibiting failure. Generally, the samples reinforced with jute fibre displayed ductile failure and showcased residual strength after surpassing the peak stress. This behaviour aligns with findings documented in prior studies on fibre reinforced compressed earth [4,124–126].

3.2.6. Crack propagation analysis

Once the FRSREM specimens were tested to determine strength, SEM was used to visually assess the influence of jute fibre

Fig. 5. Results of compression testing (A) and flexural testing (B) of mortars.

reinforcement on the surface morphology and topography. As shown in Fig. 6, the fibre reinforcement could be seen spanning cracks within the test samples, demonstrating its ability to distribute stress and resist crack propagation, thus enhancing the material's load-bearing capacity.

However, it was observed that some fibres ran parallel with the fracture (Fig. 6A), which would provide little to no benefit in transferring stress across the failure plane. The effectiveness of the fibre reinforcement depends on the position and orientation of the fibres in the regions of high stress. To optimise the performance of fibre reinforced composites, it is important to achieve an effective distribution of fibres throughout the sample [127], which can be attained through mechanical mixing methods [81]. In some cases (Fig. 6B) evidence of stress transfer could be seen at the location of fibres, demonstrated by the presence of microscopic cracks (approximately 1–5 μm in width) perpendicular to the main fracture. Remarkably, the majority of fibres remained undamaged which suggests the failure mechanism was through fibre pull-out, rather than the rupture of the fibre itself.

3.2.7. Statistical analysis

The results of the statistical analysis are presented in Table 10, whereby statistically significant differences are indicated by different letters (A, B, C). The results demonstrate that the addition of cement in the SREM specimen caused a statistically significant increase in compressive and flexural strength when compared to the REM specimens. Furthermore, the statistical analysis also demonstrates that the addition of jute fibre reinforcement in the FRSREM samples caused a statistically significant increase in compressive and flexural strength when compared to the REM and the SREM specimens. This is an important finding, as it demonstrates that the incorporation of jute fibre effectively enhances the mechanical properties of SREM.

3.3. Shear triplet testing

3.3.1. Shear strength

The results of the shear-triplet testing are presented in Fig. 7. A linear regression line is plotted between the data points, as per BS EN 1052-3:2002 [64]. The angle of internal friction is determined from the gradient of the regression line and the point at which the regression line intercepts the vertical axis is the initial shear strength at zero normal stress.

As presented in Fig. 6, shear triplets containing REM achieved the lowest initial shear strength of 0.198 MPa. In comparison, shear triplets containing SREM and FRSREM demonstrated an initial shear strength of 0.262 MPa and 0.280 MPa, representing an increase of approximately 32 % and 41 %, respectively. These results are greater than the minimum required values outlined in BS EN 998-2:2016 [19], whereby the characteristic initial shear strength must be at least 0.15 MPa for general-purpose and lightweight mortar. Furthermore, the results also exceed the minimum required values outlined in DIN 18946:2018 [61], whereby the characteristic initial shear strength of earth-based mortar must be at least 0.04 MPa.

The shear strength of the shear triplet specimens is influenced by several factors, including the mortar composition, the surface characteristics of the masonry unit and the moisture content of the masonry unit at the time of construction [25,38,66]. The surface characteristics and the moisture content of the CEBs remained constant, therefore, the difference in shear strength may be attributed to the mortar composition and characteristics.

3.3.2. Influence of cement stabilisation and fibre reinforcement

Within the REM specimens, the clay fraction serves as the binder and establishes a bond with the CEB through a combination of electrostatic forces, cementation, capillarity, electromagnetic forces and friction [26,27]. Within existing literature [38,40], the initial shear strength of REM typically ranges from 0.018 to 0.16 MPa, therefore an initial shear strength of 0.198 MPa is considered high for a raw earth mortar, indicating that a strong bond was achieved. The high porosity of the un-stabilised CEBs and the process of

Fig. 6. Sem images showing jute fibre bridging the gap between the cracks in FRSREM

Table 10
Statistical significance of mortar test results.

Test	Mortar Mix		
	REM	SREM	FRSREM
Compression Test (Half Prism)	A	B	C
Flexural Test (Prism)	A	B	C

Fig. 7. Results of shear triplet testing.

pre-wetting likely contributed to the development of this bond [38,39]. The presence of differential shrinkage between two bonded materials is generally known to cause undesirable stress at the bond interface resulting in a reduction in bond strength [128]. Therefore, the relatively high linear shrinkage observed in the REM will likely have an adverse influence on the bond strength.

The shear triplet test specimens containing SREM exhibited a 32 % increase in the initial shear strength compared to those containing REM. This increase may be attributed to the incorporation of cement within the mortar and the consequential formation of hydration products, as discussed in Section 3.2.4. Alongside the creation of a solid mortar matrix, the hydration products also facilitate bonding with the porous surface of the CEBs through interlocking and crystallisation [129].

Compared to the SREM specimens, shear triplets containing FRSREM achieved an approximate 7 % increase in initial shear strength and demonstrated a 30 % increase in the angle of internal friction. This difference may be attributed to the incorporation of jute fibre reinforcement. Generally, fibre reinforcement relies on its embedment and anchorage into the surrounding material matrix to provide effective stress distribution. As there is no embedment of jute into the CEB, alternative mechanisms must contribute to the enhanced properties of the FRSREM specimens. As presented in Section 3.2.7., the incorporation of jute fibre results in a statistically significant increase in the compressive and flexural strength of the mortar. When using FRSREM in a masonry assemblage, the jute fibre will mechanically reinforce the material around the mortar bond interface. This reinforcement is believed to facilitate stress redistribution and prevent crack propagation within the mortar layer, consequently postponing shear failure. Similar characteristics are observed in concrete-to-concrete connections, whereby the presence of fibre reinforcement is known to increase the bond strength [128].

Following a review of the experimental data, a strong positive linear correlation was identified between the flexural strength of mortar (x) and initial shear strength (y) obtained from shear triplet testing, as presented in Equation (1). It is recognised that this correlation is based on a limited data set, therefore it is recommended that additional raw earth mortar mixes are investigated to further validate this relationship. Furthermore, it is acknowledged that the initial shear strength is also influenced by the properties of the masonry units, therefore the relationship proposed in Equation (1) may only apply to un-stabilised CEBs similar to those utilised in this study.

$$y = 0.0882x + 0.1541 \tag{1}$$

3.3.3. Failure modes

Different failure modes were observed during the shear triplet testing, as summarised in Table 11. Samples manufactured with REM

Table 11
Types of failure observed during testing. Illustrations obtained from [64].

Type of Failure as per BS EN 1052-3:2002	Precompression (MPa)										
	REM			SREM			FRSREM				
	0.10	0.30	0.50	0.10	0.30	0.50	0.10	0.30	0.50		
A.1 - Shear failure in the unit/mortar bond area		×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	
A.2 - Shear failure only in the mortar			×	×		×	×	×			
A.3 - Shear failure in the unit								×	×	×	

exhibited shear failure in the mortar or mortar-bond area at each magnitude of precompression. This is likely due to the relatively low bond strength and shear strength of the REM. At 0.1 MPa precompression, the samples manufactured with SREM and FRSREM exhibited failure in the mortar-bond area, similar to the failure observed in the REM specimens. However, as the precompression increased, the mode of failure transitioned to shear failure in the mortar and eventually shear failure in the CEB unit(s). This behaviour indicates that, with an increase in precompression, the capacity of the mortar bond exceeds the shear resistance of the CEB. It is recognised that the SREM and the FRSREM had significantly higher strength and stiffness compared to the un-stabilised CEBs. To ensure the failure remains within the mortar or mortar bond area, it may be preferable to select a mortar with a lower modulus than that of the masonry unit [25].

3.3.4. Microstructural analysis

Fig. 8 presents optical microscope and SEM images of the characteristic bond developed between the SREM and the CEB. Although

Fig. 8. Optical microscope (A) and SEM images (B) of the bond developed between the CEB and Mortar (SREM).

Fig. 9. Characteristic distribution of Equivalent Stress (A) and Shear Stress (B) obtained from the FEA model. Shear stress-strain relationship obtained from FEA model vs results derived from experimental analysis (C).

they were manufactured from the same base material (BS 8601), there were obvious visual differences between the stabilised mortar and the un-stabilised block. As shown in Fig. 8B, the sand particles within the SREM were enveloped in a dense mortar matrix, containing an amalgamation of clay and hydrated cement paste (C-S-H) [130]. In contrast, the sand particles in the block were sparsely coated with clay particles [131]. The dark regions within the CEB represent voids, highlighting the material's porous nature.

There is a clear transition zone between the mortar and the CEB measuring between 100 and 200 μm in width. This transition zone indicates that moisture and cementitious material successfully shifted from the fresh mortar into the pores of the block and formed a chemical and physical bond between the two materials.

3.4. Numerical modelling

FEA was undertaken to investigate the failure mechanism of the shear triplet test and provide a comparison with the results obtained from the experimental analysis. The CZM, defined in Section 2.5, was used to model the mortar-block interface and simulate the shear triplet test without precompression. This simulation replicated the experimental analysis outlined in BS EN 1052-3:2002 (Procedure B) [64]. The results of the FEA are presented in Fig. 9.

The FEA simulation calculated a maximum shear stress of 0.20, 0.26 and 0.28 MPa for the shear triplet samples containing REM, SREM and FRSREM, respectively. As shown in Fig. 9C, the results obtained from the FEA are within $\pm 5.0\%$ of the expected values derived from experimental analysis. Moreover, the stress-strain curves derived from the simulation exhibit behaviour consistent with those observed during testing, and regions of high stress (Fig. 9A & B) match the areas of cracking and deformation observed during the experimental examination. The results of the FEA demonstrate that the CZM method of modelling provides a satisfactory correspondence to the results and behaviour obtained from experimental analysis.

Following the successful validation of the CZM, the same methodology was used to simulate the diagonal shear test of masonry assemblages, as per ASTM E519-E519M:2022 [108]. The results of the FEA simulation are presented in Fig. 10.

As presented in Fig. 10, the masonry assemblage containing REM resisted a maximum applied load of 51.8 kN, while the masonry assemblage containing SREM and FRSREM resisted 72.3 and 77.0 kN, representing an increase of 39.6% and 48.6% respectively. As anticipated, the masonry assemblage containing REM demonstrated the lowest modulus of rigidity, indicated by the gradient of the load-deformation curve, while the SREM and FRSREM demonstrated comparable characteristics.

Three failure modes and fracture patterns were observed within the FEA simulations. Masonry assemblage containing REM exhibited a horizontal slip failure along the plane of the mortar joint. This is due to the relatively low shear bond strength between the mortar and the block, leading to a sliding failure mechanism. In contrast, masonry assemblage containing SREM exhibited a mixed mode of failure whereby horizontal slip failure along the plane of the mortar joint was observed followed by conventional diagonal shear failure in the centre of the sample. Lastly, the masonry assemblage containing FRSREM exhibited a conventional diagonal shear

Fig. 10. – FEA Simulation of Diagonal Shear Test as per ASTM E519-E519M. Location crack formations (CZM bond separation) are illustrated in white.

Table 12
Results of diagonal shear test simulation.

Parameter	Mortar Mix		
	REM	SREM	FRSREM
Failure Load, P (N)	51,840	72,291	76,988
Shortening in the Direction Parallel to Loading, Δ_x (mm)	9.98	10.98	11.48
Extension in the Direction Perpendicular to Loading, Δ_y (mm)	2.04	2.48	2.64
Net Area of Specimen, A_n (mm ²)	186,000	186,000	186,000
Shear Stress, S_s (MPa)	0.197	0.275	0.293
Shear Strain, γ (mm/mm)	0.0069	0.0077	0.0081
Modulus of Rigidity, G (MPa)	28.75	35.80	36.34

failure originating from the position of the diagonally opposite loading shoes. The aforementioned failure modes are similar to those reported in existing research into conventional masonry walllets [40,132,133]. Within the SREM and FRSREM simulations, crushing was observed in the CEBs in contact with the loading shoe, indicating the need for the CEBs to be equivalent to or higher strength than the mortar.

The results of the FEA simulation and the subsequent calculation of shear stress, shear strain and modulus of rigidity (shear modulus) are presented in Table 12. While the results obtained from the simulation of masonry assemblages are purely theoretical, the calculated values fall within the anticipated range and, in certain instances, closely resemble the findings from experimental analyses documented in the existing literature [40]. However, it is anticipated that, due to the defect-free nature of the FEA simulation, the experimental analysis may attain lower values due to the potential for imperfection within the masonry assemblage.

The outcomes of the FEA simulations illustrate the effectiveness of the CZM micro-modelling methodology presented. Further analysis is recommended to simulate the behaviour and performance of full structures to optimise the design of earthen construction.

4. Conclusions

Through experimental investigation and numerical analysis, this study presented a comparative study of three different REMs. The important conclusions emerging from this study are.

- The REM, containing 68 % sand, 15 % silt, and 17 % clay, achieved an average compressive and flexural strength of 1.92 and 0.50 MPa respectively, thereby meeting the criteria for classification as an M1 mortar. The REM successfully bonded un-stabilised CEBs, achieving an initial shear strength of 0.198 MPa, meeting BS EN 998-2:2016 and DIN 18946:2018 standards.
- The addition of 20 % cement (by volume) in SREM enhanced mortar flow, reduced linear shrinkage and increased compressive, flexural and shear strength by 194 %, 140 % and 32 % respectively.
- The 0.25 %-20 mm (weight-length) jute fibre reinforcement in SREM reduced mortar flow, and linear shrinkage, leading to significant improvement in compressive (12 %) and flexural (20 %) strengths.
- The presence of jute fibre in FRSREM revealed crack bridging, indicating stress distribution and resistance to crack propagation.
- The results of the FEA were within ± 5.0 % of the expected values derived from experimental analysis and the simulation provided a satisfactory correspondence to the behaviour observed during testing.
- The FEA model predicted the failure mechanism of large-scale masonry assemblages, as per ASTM E519-E519M:2022.

The results of this investigation highlight the potential of FRSREM as a promising material for sustainable construction applications, offering enhanced mechanical properties over REM and SREM. The practical application of FRSREM will help to improve the strength of CEB assemblages and consequently improve the quality and performance of earthen houses.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jack Andrew Cottrell: Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Muhammad Ali:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Alireza Tatari:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **D. Brett Martinson:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

List of Abbreviations:

APDL	ANSYS Parametric Design Language
ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials
BS	British Standards
C-S-H	Calcium-Silicate-Hydrate
CEB(s)	Compressed Earth Block(s)
CZM	Cohesive Zone Model
DIN	Deutsches Institut für Normung (The German Institute for Standardisation)
EN	Eurocodes
FEA	Finite Element Analysis
FRSREM	Fibre Reinforced Stabilised Raw Earth Mortar
LL	Liquid Limit
MDD	Maximum Dry Density
ME	Mortar with Earth
OMC	Optimum Moisture Content
PSD	Particle Size Distribution
PL	Plastic Limit
REM	Raw Earth Mortar
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
SREM	Stabilised Raw Earth Mortar
UoP-CEB machine	University of Portsmouth Compressed Earth Block Machine

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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